

Paper 7

THE FUNCTIONS AND JOB DESCRIPTIONS AT HOTEL INDUSTRY: A CASE OF GRAND HYATT, MUMBAI

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Abstract:

The training and working in the Hotel industry will gives the true light. It will help to realize that Hotel Industry is much more than just fun & pleasure; it's a lot of hard work. There are multiple departments with junior and senior cedars professionals. Each person is unique in nature have different talents to contribute in the industry as a team. Every job has its nuances and its value and that no job is superior to the other. When a person want to sustain in the industry, have to improve constantly. A student in a hotel industry has to keep documentation and try hard to gain experience along with their studies in college. This paper will throw light on the different department and the job descriptions at Grand Hyatt and it is purely a case study. The Hierarchy which exists in the hotel industry for the smooth functioning of the Hotel is explained in this study.

Keywords: Hotel Industry, departments, practical skills, profession, customers.

1. INTRODUCTION

The story of Hyatt hotels and resorts, which opened its first hotel in 1957, is a tale of continual innovation, remarkable expansion and a single-minded dedication to the highest of standards. The US-based company has, for nearly 50 years, transformed the hospitality industry by combining friendliness and efficiency with the finest traditions of international hotel keeping. In the process, Hyatt has redefined luxury for the modern traveler. Hyatt Hotels Corporation is an American multinational owner, operator, and franchiser of hotels, resorts, and vacation properties. The Hyatt Corporation came into being upon purchase of the Hyatt House, at Los Angeles International Airport, on September 27, 1957. In 1969, Hyatt opened its first hotel outside the United States, the Hyatt Regency Hong Kong. In 1980 the Grand Hyatt and Park Hyatt brands were introduced. Hyatt runs resort hotels, starting with the Hyatt Regency Maui in 1980. As of 30 November 2015 Hyatt had over 627 hotels worldwide. As of March 25, 2018, Hyatt has 777 properties in 54 countries. In 2018, Fortune magazine listed Hyatt as the 9th best U.S. Company to work for.

2. PROFILE OF GRAND HYATT MUMBAI

Hyatt Mission, Goal and Values: The mission is to provide authentic hospitality by making a difference in the lives of the people we touch every day, including our associates, guests

and owners. The goal is to be the most preferred brand in each customer segment that we serve for our associates, guests and owners. We aim to foster a common purpose and culture within the Hyatt family through shared core values of mutual respect, intellectual honesty and integrity, humility, fun, creativity and innovation. The mission, goal and values are interdependent, and refer to this interdependence as the “Hyatt value chain.” The Hyatt value chain begins with their associates. They believe that their efforts to engage their associates in planning for how they can better serve their fellow associates, guests and owners contributes to their commitment to genuine service, which is the first step to achieving high levels of guest satisfaction

Overview: Grand Hyatt Mumbai is a luxury 5-star hotel located off the Western Express Highway, Santacruz (East) in Mumbai, India. Designed by Chicago's Lohan Associates, Grand Hyatt Mumbai was opened in 2004.

Infrastructure and Amenities: The hotel has a total of 547 rooms and 111 serviced apartments built on an area of about 12 acres. The banquet level of the hotel offers nearly 30,000 square feet/2,790 square meters of conference and meeting space including one fully wired ball rooms in the city; seven additional meeting rooms and board rooms and a pre-function area. It also has four specialty restaurants — China House, Celini, Soma and Fifty Five East; which serve Indian and international cuisines. It also has a Bar, lounges, Gourmet Store, fitness center and a beauty salon which are situated inside a multi-level shopping plaza. It also has a Grand Club, Club Oasis spa, pool area and barbecue area for Residences; Kids play area, Business Center, outdoor recreation facilities and facilities for physically challenged guests and single women travelers. The hotel also has one of the largest collections of art in a public space in India that showcases over 100 commissioned pieces of art by established and upcoming artists curate in collaboration with Rajeev Sethi

Grand Hyatt Mumbai, India: This luxury hotel and residential development sits on 12 acres located just 20 minutes south of Mumbai’s international airport. The five-star property includes 547 guestrooms, 110 serviced apartments, a business center, health spa, fitness center, pools, and 10,000 square meters of retail. In addition to the pools, outdoor recreational facilities include basketball, tennis and volleyball courts, as well as a paved jogging path. The property is distinguished by stunning water features, distinctive hard cape elements and lush landscaping, as well as many sculptures and other works of art throughout. Due to its proximity to the airport, the structure could not be more than six stories tall, and local mandates required that 15 percent of the site remain open. To attract major conferences and India’s customary weeklong wedding celebrations, the hotel includes a 1,000-seat grand ballroom, meeting rooms, four restaurants, an entertainment center, and below-grade parking for 700 cars.

Places to visit in Mumbai: *Bandra:* Located 20 minutes away from Grand Hyatt Mumbai, Bandra is a prominent entertainment and culture hub in Mumbai. Termed as the ‘Queen of Suburbs’, Bandra is a melting pot of activity and culture; showcasing a cross section of lifestyle products and services, restaurants, pubs, bars and high-street stores. *Bandra-Worli Sea link:* Opened in 2009, The Bandra Worli Sea link also known as the Rajiv Gandhi Sea link is a cable-stayed bridge that connects the suburbs of Mumbai to the arterial roads of downtown Worli and South Mumbai; the richest urban precinct in India that places the city’s main business areas, prime office spaces and high-end residential facilities within itself. *Worli:* A key commercial district in Mumbai, Worli is home to a congregation of

multinational companies like Novartis, GSK Pharma, Barclays Bank, Credit Suisse, Hindujas, YES Bank and Maersk Shipping. *Bandra Kurla Complex and Kalina*: Bandra Kurla complex (BKC); an emerging business district centrally located in the heart of Mumbai. It is home to international schools such as the Dhirubai Ambani International School and the American School of Bombay (ASB).

3.THE DEPARTMENTS

a. FOOD & BEVERAGE SERVICE: *Food and Beverage Outlets: Celini:* Exuding an understating elegance, Celini's interiors are contemporary and simple, using interesting textures of natural wood, stone and matte-finishes steel. The truly Italian home-style cooking embraces traditional Italian recipes and presents them with a modern approach. Inspired by the restaurants wood fired ovens, rotisserie and charcoal grill, Celini's authentic cuisine is prepared in an open show kitchen. **Soma:** A palate of Indian food and art, Soma's modern interior, bold artwork and cotemporary furnishing conspires to create a unique concept for the restaurant. Soma offers regional and tandoor grilled cuisine, simple but delicious it offers a fantastic array of flavours. The theatrically lit tandoor show kitchen is the restaurants central feature where you can see the skilled chefs preparing food right before your eyes. **Fifty Five East:** A casual dining restaurant featuring interactive kitchens which offer Thai, Lebanese, sushi, Western and Indian specialities prepared a la minute. The design of the restaurant draws inspiration from the natural phenomena of sunlight passing through leaves and branches in a forest, the result is a textured look with uneven shadows in harmony with each other. Melding the eclectic energies of Asian cuisine with unlimited glasses of one of France's premium champagnes, The Essence Brunch is the ultimate showcase of taste and temptation, flavor and flamboyance. **Lobby Lounge:** A stylish contemporary lounge offering an all-day dining menu. The lobby lounge offers an eclectic mix of Indian and international specialties, afternoon high tea as well as canapé menu. One of the highlights of the beverage menu is the premium selection of Indian single estate teas. **China House Lounge:** Multi-faceted in spirit, China House Lounge serves as a versatile retreat and the ideal place to linger after dinner over a drink or party to the high- energy music spun by the in-house DJ. **The Bar:** A great place to unwind after a long day. Select from a range of vintage wines by the glass, finest whiskies and exclusive single malts. **Gourmet Store:** Located at ground level of the hotel's Shopping plaza, the Gourmet Store is a one-top hopping destination for a range of food products such as homemade breads, chocolates, cookies, cheese, meat selection, sandwiches, salads, cakes, pastries and some retail food beverage products. There are also varieties of coffee, tea, soft drinks, shakes and other beverages. **Aqua:** The poolside bar is the idea place to reflex after a swim at the pool. The refreshing Aqua menu features a variety of beverages in addition to delectable snack menu. **Banquets:** As we all know Grand Hyatt Mumbai is known for his banquets. Grand Hyatt Mumbai's banquet is spread out over a large area in the hotel. It involves 10 meeting rooms and one huge ballroom and a Grand lawn. The hotel holds various functions like award functions, weddings, meetings, concerts etc. With over 30,000 sq. feet/2,790 sq. meters of sophisticated, indoor banquet space on offer, including one of the largest ballrooms; seven additional smaller venues, a spacious pre-function area and a dedicated Events team, we help you translate your dream wedding to an opulent reality; the way you have always imagined it to be! 100

The hotel has different venues all the events and functions: **The Grand Ballroom:** The size of the pillar less ballroom 11,600 sq.ft/1075 sq.meter. The height of the ceiling is 24 feet. The ballroom can be partitioned into three sound proof sections ranging from 325 to 400 sq.meter

each. It can accommodate 450-1500 in a cocktail reception style. **The Grand Salon:** The modern and elegant grand salon is 2.184 sq.ft/196 sq.meter. It can accommodate 120-150 guests in a cocktail reception style. It can be divided into 3 separate partitions ranging from 72-84 sq meters. **Mahogany:** The Mahogany is of 1104 sq.ft/98.sq meters. It can accommodate 50 guests for a cocktail function and it can accommodate 40 guests for an elegant and formal seating. **Boardroom:** The boardroom is of 1680 sq.ft/ 156 sq meters and is used for smaller functions and events. It can accommodate 40 guests and it has warm and welcoming atmosphere for the guests. **Drawing Room:** The drawing room is mostly used for smaller but private functions. It can have private receptions and cocktail evenings. It can accommodate 60 guests with the seating of couches and sofas. It has a lower and upper deck. The size of the room is 1890 sq.ft/185 sq meter.

b. JOB DESCRIPTION

Job Description of Food and Beverage Director: Reports To: General Manager; **Position Summary:** The Director of Food & Beverage is responsible for coordinating all phases of group meeting/banquet functions held in the Hotel; coordinate these activities on a daily basis; assist clients in program planning and menu selection. **Duties and Responsibilities:** Achievement of budgeted food sales, beverage sales, labour costs and profitability; Completion of Customer Follow-up calls on a timely basis; Timely analysis of Food & Beverage Prices in relation to competition; Participation and input towards F&B Marketing activities; Supervision of daily paper flow including Proposals, and Function Contracts; Preparation of Sales Promotions & Mailings; Directly responsible for large function billings and overseeing medium/small function billings with particular regard to accuracy and timeliness (48 hours); Evaluation forms must accompany all invoices; Gather for large events; oversee for medium/small events, guaranteed attendance numbers. They are required 3 business days in advance of functions.

Job Description of Assistant Food and Beverage Manager: Reports to: Food and Beverage Manager. **Position summary:** An assistant director of food and beverage is one who looks after the administration of the hotel staff, which caters to the needs of the customers. He is a senior team management member who will direct the staff in deciding the various cuisines, and other factors to the likes of the customer to facilitate the smooth functioning of the hospitality trade. **Duties and Responsibilities:** Taking orders from the director and bring them to the staff; Discuss the budget and accordingly plan the inventory, chart menu cards along with their prices in the approval of the director; Supervise over the activities of the staff to get the desired tastes to the likes of the customers; Take the approval of the directors in case of large orders like organizing of parties and marriage banquets; Oversee the duties carried out on day to day basis; provide the inventory and funds required on need; Watch over the paper work done while noting down day to day expenses, direct the staff to record the daily expenses incurred.

Job Description of Outlet Manager: Reports to: Assistant Food And Beverage Director. **Position summary:** Manages daily outlet operations and assists with menu planning maintains sanitation standards and assists servers and hosts on the floor during peak meal periods. Strives to continually improve guest and employee satisfaction and maximize the financial performance in areas of responsibility. **Duties and responsibilities:** Supervises food and beverage service staff in accordance with operating policies that he or she may help establish; Creates a positive team atmosphere among Team Members; Maintains records of

staff periodic manner and operating costs; Provides feedback and coaching to the Team regularly; Understands building capability through Cross training; Sets high standards for appropriate team behaviour on shift.

c. FOOD PRODUCTION

Main Kitchens of the hotel are: Celini kitchen, Soma kitchen, China House kitchen, Fifty Five East kitchen, Gourmet Store kitchen, Banquet kitchen, Bakery, Pastry, Butchery, Chocolate room, Staff kitchen and Gard manger. **Celini live kitchen:** Celini kitchen embraces traditional Italian recipes and presents them with a modern approach. Exuding an understated elegance, the interiors of Celini are contemporary and simple. The Mumbai restaurant showcases a wood-fired pizza oven, rotisserie and charcoal grill – all built into its show kitchen designed by Molteni of France, where the sights and smells of Chef Alessandro Persico’s Italian cooking invades all the senses. The restaurant has an exhaustive list of delectable wine and multiple seating options like table booths and lounge. **Soma live kitchen:** Indian restaurant Soma offers authentic specialties from North India and the North-West frontier cuisine. The food at the best Indian restaurant in Mumbai is simple, with a selection of tandoor-grilled meats, seafood and vegetables, each prepared live to perfection. The tandoor show kitchen at Soma is the restaurant’s central feature, allowing diners to see skilled chefs preparing the meal right before their eyes. The colorful and eclectic art at Soma restaurant in Mumbai reflects the moon in its serene traditional moods, providing the ideal ambience for savoring authentic and traditional Indian cuisine. The restaurant has an exhaustive wine list and unique desserts. **China House live Kitchen:** China House, the best Chinese restaurant in Mumbai offers casual dining with a modern approach. China House offers delectable signature dishes such as Beggar’s Chicken, hand-pulled Dan Dan noodles, Peking Duck, Black pepper king crab, Steamed crystal prawn dumplings; that are complemented by an exhaustive list of delectable wines and a host of mouth-watering desserts to cleanse the palate. The China House restaurant design integrates interactive glass show kitchens into a multiple-seating layout with table booths and lounge. **Fifty Five East live Kitchen:** Fifty Five East is a casual dining restaurant in Mumbai featuring interactive kitchens, offering Thai, Japanese, Lebanese mezze, Western and Indian specialties prepared à la minute. Fifty Five East restaurant is also known for its exhaustive wine list and is popular for its business luncheons and Sunday brunches. **Gourmet Store Kitchen:** The Gourmet Store kitchen features a large selection of gourmet delicatessen items such as cheeses, cold cuts, home-made salads, meats and made-to-order sandwiches, as well as coffee, an array of teas, smoothies and milkshakes, which are available to take away or be consumed in the Gourmet Store. A selection of cakes, breads, decorative pastries and cookies in specially designed packaging are also offered. **Banquet kitchen:** It is the main area of kitchen which provides food for banquet functions in areas like Pre-function area, Ballrooms, Boardrooms and Mahogany room. **Bakery:** The Bakery of Grand Hyatt provides varieties of baked goods and different types of breads like Ciabatta, Focaccia, French baguettes Brioche etc; to all other outlets.

Job Description of Executive Chef: Reports To: General Manager. **Position Summary:** Responsible for the consistent preparation of innovative and creative cuisine of the highest quality, presentation and flavor for the dining rooms, banquets and other food facilities, resulting in outstanding guest satisfaction. **Duties and Responsibilities:** Trains, develops and motivates supervisors and culinary staff to meet and exceed established food preparation standards on a consistent basis; Teaches preparation according to well defined recipes and

follows up and discusses ways of constantly improving the cuisine at the property; Display exceptional leadership by providing a positive work environment, counselling employees as appropriate and demonstrating a dedicated and professional approach to management; Should be able to provide direction for all day-to-day operations in the kitchen; Determines how food should be presented, and create decorative food displays; Recognizes superior quality products, presentations and flavor; Ensures compliance with food handling and sanitation standards.

Job Description of Executive Sous Chef: Reports To: Executive Chef. **Position Summary:** The Executive Sous Chef is responsible to assist the Executive Chef for overall kitchen operation as a successful independent profit center, ensuring maximum guest satisfaction, through planning, organizing, directing, and controlling the Kitchen operation and administration. Exhibits culinary talents by personally performing tasks while assisting in leading the staff and managing all food related functions. Also assists in supervising all kitchen areas to ensure a consistent, high quality product is produced. **Duties and Responsibilities:** Interacts with guests to obtain feedback on product quality and service levels; Responds to and handles guest problems and complaints; Able to make recommendations to the Executive Chef regarding succession planning; To be aware of all financial budgets and goals; To ensure that guests are always receiving an exceptional dining experience representing true value for money; Ensure that all recipes and product yields are accurately costed and reviewed regularly; Ensure that all food items are prepared as per standard recipe cards whilst maintaining portion control and minimizing waste.

Job Description of Pastry Chef: Reports to: Executive Chef / Sous Chef. **Position Summary:** A Pastry chef is responsible to create high quality pastry dishes with the standard recipes and presentations in order to maintain quality standards and consistency of product. Also assist in production and maintenance of par stocks of pastry and dessert with proper rotation of products and maintain highest cleanliness and hygiene standard in the pastry and bakery section. **Duties and Responsibilities:** Manages all day-to-day operations of the pastry and bakery section of the kitchen; prepare a wide variety of goods such as cakes, cookies, pies, bread etc. following traditional and modern recipes; Able to produce all baked goods including but not limited to artisan breads and rolls, muffins, laminated Danish, laminated croissants and doughnuts etc; Decorate pastries and desserts using different types of icings, toppings etc. and ensure the food presentation will be beautiful and exciting; Monitor stocks for baking ingredients such as flour, sugar etc. and make appropriate orders within budget; Check quality of material and condition of equipment and devices used for cooking. 38

Job Description of Grade Manager: Reports to: Executive Chef. **Position Summary:** Responsible for managing the food production and quality control for all meat, fish, fowl and other food items prepared in the cold kitchen. **Duties and Responsibilities:** Oversee the consistency of various preparations within the cold kitchen to ensure quality product and adherence to standard recipes; Prepares all cold food according to recipes, guidelines and standards set by the Executive Chef or hotel standards; Ensures that assigned work area has proper level of par stocks and supplies according to daily production sheets (based on house count), daily menus and banquets events; Always keep all refrigeration, equipment, storage and working areas in clean, working condition in order to comply with health department regulations; Delegates and assists in preparing of cold food items like salads, sushi, cold cuts, salad dressings etc.

d. FRONT OFFICE

The front office is the part of an organization that comes in contact with guests, marketing, sales, and service departments. In the hotel industry, the front office (also known as front desk) welcomes guests to the accommodation section: meeting and greeting them, taking and organizing reservations, allocating check in and out of rooms, organizing porter service, issuing keys and other security arrangements, passing on messages to customers and settling the accounts. A hotel front desk agent represents the first point of contact with guests and handles all stages of a guest's stay. A typical day as a hotel front desk agent, involves registering/booking guests in and out of their rooms, while accommodating any special requests.

Front Desk: The **hotel front desk** is the reception area of the hotel. Those at the desk basically keep the hotel operating, with its many responsibilities. It is the front desk staff that checks guests in and assigns them a room. Front desk staff is also in charge of sending hotel staff to clean the rooms that have been used. Guests also come to the front desk to ask questions and to check out when they are done. A guest's experience at a hotel is largely dependent on the treatment experienced by the hotel staff, especially those at the front desk. The front desk staff represents the hotel in the eyes of guests. **Reservations:** Reservation office, takes care of booking or reserving of a room (accommodation) by a guest. Reservations leads to reserving of a particular type of room for a particular guest for a given period of time. It also gives the guest the first impression of the hotel. Reservations involve activities which do not take place in front of the guests. The entire front office activities start the moment an enquiry or request regarding accommodation is made at the reservations. 91

Guest Relations Executive (GRE): A Guest Relation Officer, also known as a Guest Relation Coordinator or Guest Relation Specialist, is a customer service-oriented employee who essentially greets hotel guests. From escorting guests to rooms to assisting in arranging reservations, Guest Relation Officers ensure a pleasant and satisfying stay at a hotel. They also handle guest complaints, assist with the check-in process and explain all facility amenities, such as pool areas and restaurants. **Skills of a Guest Relations Executive:** Since Guest Relation Officers spend a great deal of time interacting with guests, it is important that they have strong communication, interpersonal and listening skills. They should also be aggressive problem-solvers and have the ability to manage crises successfully. Above average organizational and time management skills are also critical for Guest Relation Officers. Being detail-oriented and possessing the ability to work closely in teams also contributes to the success of this position.

The Concierge: Concierges specialize in guest services at hotels, but some work in clubs and restaurants. Separate from other guest services workers, concierges usually provide guests with information and advice about locations and services outside of the hotel. Concierges often call taxis to transport guests and arrange storage for packages and luggage. Hotel concierges provide guests with highly specialized services meant to improve guest experiences. Some concierges acquire event tickets for guests, which could involve making reservations or payment under a guest's name. Concierges may also arrange guided tours and other special activities for guests. In case of emergencies, concierges help guests locate medical facilities, dentist offices or veterinary care hospitals.

Guest Service Centre (GSC): Guest service centre is a part of back office operations where the Guest Service agents answer telephone calls from guests seeking to make or cancel hotel reservations. Agents answer guest requests for assistance and coordinate with housekeeping, bell service, staff and management to fulfill guest requirements. They provide guests with access to hotel services, forward in-room meal requests, and ensure that mail, faxes and packages are delivered in a timely manner. Agents also deal with irate guests and find ways to resolve issues to the guest's satisfaction. They may also serve as concierges, assisting guests with ground transportation, restaurant or entertainment reservations, and providing other information about the locale. Agents may also be responsible for bookkeeping duties, including maintaining a cash drawer, preparing bank deposits and posting charges for items that guests may order or use during their stay. Upon checkout, agents calculate the guest's final bill and collect payments.

Bell Desk: A bellman is a hotel employee primarily in charge of transporting the luggage from the car to the hotel room and back. A bellman may also load or unload luggage from the car, store luggage for the guests, help guests with packages and find lost luggage. After the guests check in at the front desk, the bellman will escort the guests to their hotel room. The bellman should tell guests about the rooms' features as well as the services that are available in the hotel.

Job Description of Rooms Division Manager: Reports to: General Manager. **Position summary:** The Rooms Division Manager is responsible for Executive Housekeeping and Front Office. He/she manages the general operation of the Front Office e.g. Reception, Reservations, Concierge, Switchboard and Night Manager. **Duties and responsibilities:** The position's main duties are divided in spot checking of hotel rooms to ensure standards, authorizing all leave schedules or ensuring control of expenditures as well as budgets set. A RDM attends weekly executive and sales meetings as well as the General Manager's briefings with Front Office and Housekeeping. For that a Rooms Division Manager needs clear, concise written and verbal communication skills at his/her disposal, as well as strong organizational, excellent time management skills and technical skills; Reporting directly into the Executive Assistant Manager (Rooms), your responsibilities will include but not be limited to ensure timely, efficient & professional welcome and check-in is provided by all Front Desk Colleagues ensuring customer satisfaction; Maintain a high morale and productivity as well as good communication within the Front Office as well as between other departments; Develop colleagues, Team Leaders and Managers by delegating tasks and then empower and coach them making sure they achieve the desired results; Monitor the level of service provided by the department (i.e. by analyzing the Guest Satisfaction Reports) and constantly working on improving it through investigation, analysis and corrective action; Prepare the departmental budget and put measures in place to achieve or exceed the budgeted profit. 100

Job Description of Front Office Manager: Reports to: Rooms Division Manager. **Position summary:** Directly supervises all front office personnel and ensures proper completion of all front office duties. Directs and coordinates the activities of the front desk, reservations, guest services, and telephone areas. Prepare monthly reports and budget for front office department. **Duties and responsibilities:** Trains, cross –trains, and re-trains all front office personnel; Participates in the selection of front office personnel; Schedules the front office staff; Supervises workload during shifts; Evaluates the job performance of each front office

employee; Maintains working relationships and communicates with all departments; Maintains master key control; Verifies that accurate room status information is maintained and properly communicated; Resolves guest problems quickly, efficiently, and courteously; Updates group information. Maintains, monitors, and prepares group requirements. Relays information to appropriate personnel.

Job Description of Guest Relations Executive: Reports to: Front Office Manager. **Position summary:** Attend to guests courteously and deal promptly with their requests and queries. Have Detailed information about the hotel and city. Check on VIP guest movements, complete their pre-registration formalities. Allocate rooms to all arriving guests after checking the guest preferences. Collect guest feedback forms and do any possible first hand service recovery steps. **Duties and responsibilities:** Welcome guests during check-in and giving a fond farewell to guest while checkout; Handling guest complaints and concerns in an efficient and timely manner; Overseeing VIP guests, arrivals and departures; Coordinating and multi-tasking job duties in a busy environment; Should possess detailed information about the Hotel, city as well as the competition; Detailed information regarding arrivals and room requirements; Providing information regarding the Hotel, town attractions, activities etc; Check on VIP reservations, complete their pre-registration formalities; Allocate rooms to all arriving guests.

Job Description of Bell Desk Captain: Reports to: Duty Manager. **Position summary:** Primarily responsible for the supervision of all bell desk staffs, activities and also up keeping of desk area. The bell captain is also responsible for welcoming all guests to the hotel as well as bidding them with a fond farewell. He should make sure all luggage, letter, courier and message movements are tracked and accounted. **Duties and responsibilities:** Ensure that bell desk is manned at all times; Keep working area, clean and tidy always; Ensure that smooth and fast baggage handling for all arrival / departure guests; Maintain close relationship with reception / information / cashier as well as other departments; Attend all guest calls for Bell stand / Door Services related services; Delegate bell boys to pick up the baggages from guest rooms.; Errand cards are filled in for all baggage movements (Check-in, Check-out, Left luggage etc.)

e. HOUSEKEEPING

Housekeeping is a department that deals essentially with cleanliness. The guest satisfaction is its primary objective and the hygiene factor must always be present in the hotel. **Task:** To be responsible for the guest rooms, back of the house and front of the house; To ensure cleanliness, maintenance, hygiene and safety of the hotel; To ensure guest receives high quality services; To ensure that the brand standard are applied; **Areas within housekeeping department:** Rooms, Public area, Laundry, Uniform room, Pest control, Mini-bar and flower rooms.

Job Description of Executive House Keeping: Report to: General Manager. **Position Summary:** Supervises all housekeeping employees, has the authority to hire or discharge, plans and assigns work assignments, give training for newly recruited employees, audit and inspects housekeeping personal work assignment and requisition supplies. Take care of the budget and budget controlling for the department. **Duties and responsibilities:** Supervises all housekeeping employees, hires new employees as needed, discharges employees when necessary and take disciplinary actions when policies are not followed. Evaluates employees

in order to upgrade them when openings arise; Plans the work for the housekeeping department and distributes assignments accordingly. Assigns regular duties and special duties for housekeeping staff. Schedules employees and assigns extra days off according to occupancy forecast; Maintains a time log book of all employees within the department; Recruit and train new employees. Assigns new employees to work with experienced help. Checks on the work of these employees occasionally and observes the report made by the supervisors.

Job Description of Assistant Executive Housekeeper: Reports: Executive Housekeeper. **Position Summary:** The Assistant Executive Housekeeper supervises and coordinates activities of room attendant, house attendant, public area cleaners and floor supervisors. He / She assists in the managing and directing of the day-to-day operations of all Housekeeping and laundry functions. **Duties and responsibilities:** Should have an eye for detail and the ability to effectively deal with guests, other departments and housekeeping staff; Obtains list of vacant rooms to be cleaned immediately & list of prospective checkouts or discharges in order to prepare work assignments; Experience with turn down service, special needs of VIP Guests, foreign dignitaries, etc. is helpful; Assigns team members their duties, and inspects work for conformance to prescribed standards of cleanliness; Prepares and distributes the Room assignment sheet and floor keys to room boys; Maintain clear and efficient communication and coordination with the Front Office and other departments of the hotel; Schedules the cleaning of the room carpets, upholstery, and draperies as needed, along with deep cleaning projects and window cleaning as necessary. 86

Job Description of Laundry Manager: Report to: Executive Housekeeper / Asst. Executive housekeeper. **Position Summary:** A Laundry Manager is responsible for running laundry departments day to day operations and also to deliver an excellent Guest experience while managing stock ordering and supplier relationships. **Duties and responsibilities:** Developing and putting into operation the current system and technical advancement in the field of Laundry operations; Formulating washing formula for stained loads; Ensuring the washing of linen and uniform as per standard; Maintenance and upkeep of all laundry equipment; Co-ordinating with the Engineering Department about their routine maintenance of the equipment; Preparing Annual Laundry Budget; Record and monitor laundry cost.

Job Description of Guest Room Attendant: Reports To : House Keeping Supervisor **Position Summary:** Performs routine duties in cleaning and servicing of guest rooms and baths under supervision of housekeeping supervisor. Room attendant promotes a positive image of the property to guests and must be pleasant, honest, and friendly and should also able to address guest requests and problems. **Duties and responsibilities:** Enters and prepares the room for cleaning; Makes bed; Dusts the room and furniture; Replenishes guestroom and bath supplies; Cleans the bathroom; Cleans the closet; Vacuums and racks the carpet; Checks and secures the rooms; Replenish amenities according to the operational standards; Deliver and retrieve items on loan to guests e.g. iron and ironing boards; Ensure security of guest rooms and privacy of guests; Cleans guest bathroom/bed room/floor corridor.

Job Description of Florist: Reports To: Executive Housekeeper / Asst Executive Housekeeper. **Position Summary:** As a Florist / Floral Designer the primary responsibility is to create innovative floral décor and lead floral installation for the hotel lobby, Guest Rooms,

Restaurants, Spa and other public areas. Have a good coordination with the housekeeping and as well as other department like Front office, F&B Service in order to cater to their floral requirements. **Duties and responsibilities:** Able to create visually appealing flower arrangements for hotels daily requirements; Able to provide specialized design and floral expertise to plan, design and create floral arrangements for all events in the hotel eg: Weeding, Engagement, product launch etc; Able to preparing bouquets for guests, lobby centre pieces and other flower arrangement as per request or memo from both housekeeping and other departments; Assist with loading or unloading of flowers and props from vehicles as and when required; Ensure that all designs meet hotels standards and meet or exceed guests expectations.

Room Supplies: Bath rooms; Moisturizer, Cotton tips, Cotton, wipes, Comb, Disposable bags, Shower cap, Shampoo, Soap, Dental kit, Shaving kit, Emery board, Body lotion, Ear buds, Water bottles, Toilet rolls, Hair dryer and Napkin. Writing table: Telephone, Business kit, Lamp, Newspaper, Magazine, TV remote, Scribbling pad, TV guide, Wardrobe and Iron. Wardrobe: Hangers, Pillow, Bathrobe, Safe, Laundry slip, Shoe shine, Shoe mitt, Slipper, Shoe bag. Mini bar: Coke, Sprite, Diet coke, Perrier, Red bull, Beer, Whisky, Water bottle, Soda.100

f. HUMAN RESOURCES

Human Resource Management in a hotel is the management of the employees of an organization. Simply speaking, it is putting right people to the right task thereby making maximum use of the employees' talent and abilities. Human resource management is responsible for how people are treated in an organization, they deal with bringing people together in an organization, helping them perform their work, compensating them for their work and solving problems that arise. Management functions include: Staffing, Performance appraisals, Compensation and benefits, Training and development of employees and labor relations, Safety and health and Human resource research. It is strategic in nature that concerned mostly with directly assisting an organization to gain sustained competitive advantage. Its characteristic features are: Organizational Management, Personnel Administration, Manpower Management and Industrial Management.

Job Description of Director of Human Resources: Reports To: General Manager.
Position Summary: The Human Resources head oversee the daily operation of the Human Resources office. Responsible for areas of Recruiting, Employee Relations, Benefits, Events, Workers Compensation and other employee-related tasks. Additionally responsible for short and long term planning of all the HR related functions like workforce planning, recruitment, staffing strategies, wage and salary administration, associate and labour relations, benefits, workforce training and development etc.
Duties and responsibilities: To ensure that the company HR operational policies and processes are adhered to and continually improved; To assist in all activities concerning the sourcing & recruitment of staff, performance management, staff discipline and HR administration; To coordinate all matters of employee work permits and visas; To coordinate and / or conduct departmental training and conduct new hire hotel orientation program; Implement corporate policies and procedures on compensation, incentive, bonus and benefits; Continually assesses employee morale by analyzing absenteeism and turnover records, lateness and resignations; Coordinates, controls and inspects employees accommodation, staff canteen, rest rooms etc. ensuring it is of the highest possible standard of cleanliness and comfort; Coordinate employee wellness and

safety programs; Conduct needs analysis, develop, implement, and monitor training programs and materials.

Job Description of Training And Development Coordinator: Reports to: Assistant Human Resources Manager. **Summary:** The Hospitality Training and Development Coordinator is responsible for providing learning and development expertise to all locations in the Hospitality Division. This person will design programs and activities to support team effectiveness while also developing the methods to successfully measure the effectiveness of the training. **Duties and responsibilities:** Take care of entire training and development program, Handle all industrial trainees, Takes care of the budget of the department, Take feedback on various training schedules, and Keep a track on what are the latest innovations and up graduation in the market and train our employees according to them.

Job Description of Personnel Manager: Reports to: Assistant Human Resources Manager

Summary: The personnel manager is the one who manages all the people in an office. They have to look after all the professional doubts and queries that they might have. They attend to the new employees and the existing ones. **Duties and responsibilities:** Personnel managers handle all the employees in a company; They are like a bridge between the management and the staff and should help them both communicate with each other; They in consultation with the senior management, have to formulate all the company policies and implement them; They have to inform all the employees about the policy changes; They have to handle all the complaints made by the employees and have to look into all the complaints in an impartial manner; They have to design programs and events that will boost employee morale and in turn increase productivity; They have to hire employees for the company and they have to arrange for their orientation and training. Human Resource planning enables a department to project its short to long term needs on the basis of its departmental plans so that it can adjust its manpower requirements to meet changing priorities. The more changing the environment the department is in, the more the department needs manpower planning to show: o the number of recruits required in a specified timeframe and the availability of talent o early indications of potential recruitment or retention difficulties o surpluses or deficiencies in certain ranks or grades o availability of suitable qualified and experienced successors

CONCLUSION

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The original owners of the Hyatt House hotel, a luxury hotel situated near the Los Angeles Airport, were entrepreneurs Hyatt Robert von Dehn and Jack Dyer Crouch. Considering the growing use of air travel for business, the Pritzker brothers realized that locating a high quality hotel near a major airport was a valuable business strategy. Within two years, they opened another Hyatt House hotel near the San Francisco Airport and then another near the Seattle–Tacoma Airport. Over the following decade, acquisitions were made, and Hyatt became the fastest-growing hotel chain in the United States. The Grand Hyath hotel industry will have different department and work systematically for the smooth functioning of the industry. Students are also given opportunity to do their internship and study in various department, which is very useful for the students to gain knowledge along with the college education. This type of training will push trainees to both excel academically and develop practical skills. The benefits are Hotel industry continue to grow and the students who aspire to continue their studies and take profession will increase. They get experience to see the

staffs determination, commitments, so that they get an idea that the expectations of the stakeholders.

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